

Coloured Chelates of Scandium, Yttrium and Lanthanum with Chrome Azurol S

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Trisodium salt of 3'-sulpho-2''-6''-dichloro-3:3' dimethyl-4-hydroxy-fuchson-5:5' dicarboxylic acid commonly known as Chrome Azurol S forms a 1:1 chelate with scandium ($\lambda_{\max}$ 560 m μ), yttrium ($\lambda_{\max}$ 490 m μ) and lanthanum ($\lambda_{\max}$ 460 m μ). The composition and stability of these chelates have been determined by three different methods and the average values of log K for scandium, yttrium and lanthanum chelates are 5.5, 4.45 and 4.6 respectively.

Chrome Azurol S (abbrv. CAS) is a triphenylmethane type of dye and can be represented by the following structure:

The reagent possesses pronounced chelating tendencies due to the presence of donor groups like -COOH , -OH and =O and hence acts as an efficient chromogenic reagent. Spectral characteristics of CAS was for the first time studied by Malat¹ who used the spectral data to determine the dissociation constants corresponding to the different steps of dissociation. The reagent has been used as a spot test reagent by Feigl and Goldstein² and as a metallochromic indicator by others³⁻⁴. The chromogenic reactions of CAS were observed by Theis⁵ who reported that it forms coloured lakes with beryllium, copper, iron (III), aluminium, zirconium and lead. A systematic study of the colour-

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2. Feigl, F and Goldstein, D., *Anal. Chem.*, 1957, 29, 456.

3. Barnard, Jr. A. J., Broad, W. C. and Flaschka, H., *Chemist-analyst*, 1957, 46, 18.

4. Wood, J. H., *Microchim. Acta*, 1955, 11.

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ed chelated of CAS and their analytical applications in the colorimetric determination of cations was undertaken by Dey *et al.* in these laboratories⁶⁻⁷. It may be mentioned that work on the CAS chelates of scandium, yttrium, lanthanum and the rare earths has for the first time been done in these laboratories. The characteristics of the CAS chelates with scandium, yttrium and lanthanum and their stability constants have been reported in the present communication.

EXPERIMENTAL

Instruments: A Unicam SP 500 spectrophotometer and a Leeds & Northrup direct reading pH indicator were employed for absorbance and pH measurements respectively.

Materials: Stock solutions of scandium and yttrium chlorides were obtained by dissolving the Johnson Matthey samples in water containing HCl. A Johnson Matthey sample of lanthanum oxide was dissolved in conc. HCl for obtaining a stock solution of lanthanum. A stock solution of CAS was obtained by dissolving a BDH sample in distilled water.

Conditions of Study: All experiments were performed in an air conditioned room maintained at $25 \pm 1^\circ$. The pH of the solutions was adjusted to 5.0 in case of scandium and 6.0 in case of yttrium and lanthanum by adding suitable amounts of HCl or NaOH. The total volume was kept constant (25 ml) in each case. The ionic strength could not be maintained as the addition of an electrolyte caused precipitation of the chelate.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Nature of the complexes formed: Employing the method of Vosburgh and Cooper it has been determined that only one chelate is formed under the condition of study. The wavelength of maximum absorbance of CAS lies at 460 m μ (pH 5.0) and 420 m μ (pH 6.0) while those of CAS chelates with scandium, yttrium and lanthanum at 560 m μ , 490 m μ and 460 m μ respectively.

Effect of pH on the stability of the chelate: Several mixtures containing scandium, yttrium and lanthanum and CAS in the ratio 1:1 were prepared and adjusted to different pH values. The wavelength of maximum absorption of these chelates were determined at different pH and from this the range within which a particular chelate is stable has been found as shown in table I.

Composition of the chelates: Three different methods were employed for the determination of stoichiometry of these chelates, i.e., the method of continuous variation, mole ratio method and the slope ratio method. The results of all the three methods show that the composition of the chelates is 1:1 (metal: CAS) in each case. (Figs. 1-3 show the stoichiometry of scandium-CAS chelate by the three methods.

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Stability constants: The conditional stability constants have been evaluated using the method of Dey *et al.*⁸, continuous variation method using non-equimolecular solutions and the mole ratio method. The results of all the methods are in agreement with each other and are shown in table I.

Fig. 1. Composition of the scandium-CAS chelate by the continuous variations method using equimolecular solutions at pH 5.0 and 560 m μ . Concentration of the reactants.

Curve A $2.0 \times 10^{-4} M$

Curve B $1.0 \times 10^{-4} M$

Curve C $8.0 \times 10^{-3} M$

Fig. 2. Composition of the scandium-CAS chelate by the mole ratio method at pH 5.0 and 560 m μ . Concentration of CAS: Curve A. $5.0 \times 10^{-4} M$ Curve B. $9.33 \times 10^{-4} M$

TABLE I

Characteristics of CAS chelates

Temperature = 25°, Composition (metal: CAS) 1:1

Chelate	pH	pH range of stability	(a)	Log ^k (b)	(c)
Sc-CAS	5.0	3.0—6.5	5.5±0.1	5.4±0.1	5.6±0.1
Y-CAS	6.0	5.5—7.5	4.3±0.2	4.3±0.2	4.5±0.2
La-CAS	6.0	5.5—7.0	4.8±0.1	4.5±0.1	4.5±0.5

(a) Method of Dey *et al.*

(b) Method of continuous variations.

(c) Mole ratio method.

Suggestion on the structure of the chelates: CAS molecule has two positions through which the metal can form a chelating ring (i) between the adjacent carboxylic and hydroxyl oxygen and the other (ii) between the adjacent carboxylic and quinoid oxygens. The

Fig. 3 Composition of the scandium-CAS chelate by the slope ratio method at pH 5.0.

Broken lines 560 m μ

Solid lines 580 m μ

Curve AA' CAS in excess

Curve BB' scandium chloride in excess.

10 ml ($5.0 \times 10^{-4}M$) of excess component + X ml ($1.66 \times 10^{-4}M$)
variable component + (15-X) ml H₂O

electrophoresis and ion exchange adsorption studies show that the chelates of scandium, yttrium and lanthanum with CAS are neutral which can only be explained if the coordination occurs between the quinoid and adjacent carboxylic oxygen. A tentative struc-

